

Relationship Between Energy, Entropy and the Distribution Normalization Factor

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In a previous note (1), we discussed the equivalence of $-T \sum_e f(e/T) \ln(f(e/T))$ i.e. temperature times entropy and internal energy $= \sum_e e f(e)$ up to a constant related to the natural log of the normalization constant of $f(e/T)$ (divided by V , the volume). We also noted that distributions, including the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB), Juttner and Kaniadakis and the Tsallis, to an extent, made use of function-inverse function pairs. (E.g. for the MB or Juttner distribution \ln is the inverse of $\exp(-e/T)$.) In this note, we wish to examine the relationship between internal energy and entropy in more detail, in particular because F =Helmholtz free energy $= E-TS$ and Gibbs free energy $= E-TS+PV$ and we argue that $E-TS= TN \ln[1/V (m/(6.28T))^{1.5}]$ for the MB case.

Relationship Between Energy and Entropy

In the literature and in textbooks, internal energy:

$$E = \sum_e f(e) e \quad ((1)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$\text{temperature times entropy } TS/V = -T \sum_e f(e) \ln(f(e)) \quad ((2))$$

are treated as completely separate entities. Here we argue they only differ by a term related to the normalization of $f(e)$ divided by volume V . In particular, TS and not T appears because $f(e)$ is treated as $f(e/T)$ and the minus arises because $f(e)$ is proportional to $\exp(-e/T)$, hence $\ln(f)$ returns a negative sign. We argue this is significant because $E-TS$ appears in the definition of both F , Helmholtz free energy and G , Gibbs free energy, so the normalization of $f(e)$ is a key entity in statistical mechanics it seems.

Equation ((2)) may be found in (2).

In (2), it is shown that $E=N 1.5 kT$ (3 dimensions) by replacing the Sum over e with an integral over d^3p , where p is momentum.

In addition, ((2)) is evaluated, but it is not stressed how closely E and TS/V are related.

$f_0 = N/V B(T) \exp(-e/T)$ where $B(T)$ the distribution normalization factor is:

$$B(T) = [6.28 m kT]^{3/2} \quad ((3))$$

Then, from (2):

$$TS/V = TN/V \{ \ln [N/V (m / (6.28kT)^{3/2}) - 3/2] \} \quad ((4))$$

This result may be anticipated in the following way:

$$TS/V = -T \text{ Sum over } e \ f(e) \ln(f(e)) \quad \text{where } f(e)=B(T) N/V \exp(-e/T) \quad \text{Then:}$$

$$TS = E - TN \ln [N/V (B(T))] \quad ((4))$$

Thus, TS and E are the same up to the term $- TN \ln [N/V (B(T))]$ which is directly related to the Ln of B(T) the distribution normalization factor divided by V, volume. (In (3), Kaniadakis uses an unnormalized distribution $f(x) = [\text{sqrt}(1+ (kx)^2) + kx]^{1/k}$ and defines entropy as $-\int dx \ f(x) Q(f(x))$ where Q is the inverse function of f(x). Thus, similar ideas are used and TS is pretty much identical to E in that case.)

Helmholtz and Gibbs Free Energy

The idea that E and TS are very closely related seems interesting in itself because these are usually presented as being radically different entities. A link which only involves the ln of the distribution function normalization factor divided by volume seems interesting. In addition, however,

$$F=\text{Helmoltz free energy} = E-TS = TN \ln [N/V (B(T))] \quad ((5))$$

Thus, the distribution normalization constant seems to be an important statistical mechanical entity, although this does not appear to be stressed in textbooks or in the literature as far as we know.

Next, some derivatives of F from thermodynamics are calculated to investigate how the LHS of ((5)) carries important statistical mechanical information.

$$(dF/dT) \text{ at constant } V = -S \quad \text{from thermodynamics: } dF = -SdT - PdV$$

$$(dF/dT) \text{ at constant } V = N \ln [N/V (B(T))] + TN \ d/dT \ln(B) = E/T - S + TN \ d/dT \ln(B) \quad ((6))$$

Thus, one must associate the last term of ((6)) with E.

$$E/V = \text{Sum over } e \ e \ f(e) \quad \text{where } f(e) = N/V B(T) \exp(-e/T) \quad \text{Thus:}$$

$$E/V = - N/V B(T) \ d/db \ \text{Sum over } e \ \exp(-e/T) = -N/V B \ d/db \ 1/B \quad \text{where } b = 1/T \text{ and}$$

$$E/V = -N/V \ 1/T^2 \ (d/dT \ln(B)) \quad \text{Using this in ((6)) shows that:}$$

$$(dF/dT) \text{ constant } V = -S.$$

Next, one may calculate pressure $P = -d/dV$ constant T . This follows immediately from ((5)) i.e.

$P = -TN/V$ which yields the ideal gas law.

The Gibbs free energy is $F - PV$ so:

$$G = \text{Gibbs free energy} = E - TS = TN \ln [N/V (B(T))] - PV \quad ((7))$$

Using the ideal gas law (for an ideal gas only), one may write $V = NkT/P$ so that $G(T, P)$.
One sees that dG/dT T constant leads to the ideal gas law.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that internal energy E and TS are very closely related, in fact they only differ by $-NT \ln [B(T)/V]$ where $B(T)$ is the normalization constant of the distribution $f(e/T)$ e.g. the Maxwell-Boltzmann etc. In statistical mechanics, E and TS are presented as very different entities and the normalization factor of $f(e)$ is not a major statistical entity. We argue here that it is important because Helmholtz free energy $= E - TS = NT \ln [B(T)/V]$, so the \ln of $B(T)/V$ times NT represents the entire physics of the Helmholtz free energy.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Energy-Entropy, Thermodynamics and Function-Inverse Function Pairs (preprint, zenodo, 2020)
2. Huang, Kerson. Statistical Mechanics. Wiley: 1963, 1987 page 79.